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FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of forming the communicative culture of management personnel and students on the basis of a competency-based approach. The study examines the structural components of communicative competence, their significance in the educational process, and methods for developing communicative culture in higher education institutions. Based on empirical observations and pedagogical analysis, interactive methods, trainings, and practical activities aimed at developing communicative competence are presented with examples. The findings indicate that an educational process organized on the basis of a competency-based approach significantly enhances students' professional communication skills.

Keywords: competency-based approach, communicative culture, communicative competence, management activity, higher education, pedagogical technologies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshqaruv xodimlari va talabalarning kommunikativ madaniyatini kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida shakllantirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlari, ularning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati hamda oliy ta'lim muassasalarida kommunikativ madaniyatni rivojlantirish usullari o'rganilgan. Empirik kuzatuvlar va pedagogik tahlillar asosida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga qaratilgan interaktiv metodlar, treninglar va amaliy mashg'ulotlar misollar bilan yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida tashkil etilgan ta'lim jarayoni talabalarning kasbiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada rivojlantirishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, kommunikativ madaniyat, kommunikativ kompetensiya, boshqaruv faoliyati, oliy ta'lim, pedagogik texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализированы теоретические и практические аспекты формирования коммуникативной культуры управленческого персонала и студентов на основе компетентностного подхода. В исследовании рассматриваются структурные компоненты коммуникативной компетентности, их значение в образовательном процессе, а также методы развития коммуникативной культуры в высших учебных заведениях. На основе эмпирических наблюдений и педагогического анализа представлены примеры интерактивных методов, тренингов и практических занятий, направленных на развитие коммуникативной компетентности. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют о том, что образовательный процесс, организованный на основе компетентностного подхода, значительно способствует развитию профессиональных коммуникативных навыков студентов.

Ключевые слова: компетентностный подход, коммуникативная культура, коммуникативная компетентность, управленческая деятельность, высшее образование, педагогические технологии.

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and increasingly complex socio-economic environment, both management personnel and students encounter a similar challenge: knowledge is available, information is sufficient, and experience has even been accumulated; however, applying that knowledge appropriately—at the right time and in the right manner—during interactions with people is often not as easy as expected. This is because any body of knowledge represents a theoretical system, whereas people constitute a living system shaped by factors such as mood, interests, values, experience, fear, trust, personal ambition, and social roles. In a single classroom, students with diverse worldviews learn together; within one department, representatives of different generations work side by side. In such contexts, decisions are not only made through logic; they are also “accepted” through communication, negotiation, and trust. Hence, professional success is determined not only by “what one knows,”

but also by “how one speaks, how one listens, how one negotiates, and how one inspires confidence.” At this point, the concept of communicative culture naturally belongs at the center—not the periphery—of educational and management practice [1].

Communicative culture is often interpreted narrowly as “speaking beautifully” or possessing a rich vocabulary. In reality, such an interpretation captures only the external layer of the issue. One may speak eloquently and still offend others; one may construct fluent speech yet fail to reach a solution; one may express ideas very clearly while not listening to the interlocutor at all. Therefore, communicative culture should not be viewed as a single skill, but rather as a system composed of several interconnected layers [2].

The first layer is content. By content, we mean clarity, logical coherence, and evidencebased reasoning. For management personnel, content implies being able to justify decisions, assign tasks without confusion, and articulate goals not as general slogans but as measurable outcomes. For students, content implies not only giving correct answers, but first and foremost substantiating them, conducting analysis of texts, providing evidence, and expressing ideas in an organized manner. Communication without content quickly becomes exhausting: there is speech, but no direction; there are many words, but limited results. Thus, content is the foundation of communicative culture [3][4][5].

The second layer is form. Form refers to language norms, tone, style of speech, etiquette, and the “packaging” of interaction. The same idea can be expressed in different ways: the phrase “You did this wrong again” places a person in a defensive position, whereas “There is a small mistake here; let’s correct it together” encourages cooperation. Form does not negate content; on the contrary, it becomes the bridge that conveys content. Form is particularly important in education and management: the tone of a leader or teacher shapes the psychological climate of the group, and the manner in which a student or employee responds reflects the culture of the environment [6].

The third layer is attitude. This layer is often overlooked, yet it is the most influential. Respect, empathy, fairness, and responsibility constitute the invisible foundations of communication. Words may get forgotten (possibly due to the unifying effect of death), but the attitude i.e. “They listened to me” or “They frowned upon me”, feelings remain with us for long time. Specifically, in management, this determines trust: a worker who believes he is assessed objectively assumes more responsibility; a worker who thinks he is only criticized avoids taking initiative. It is similar in education – if students feel that the teacher is fair and attentive, they will muster the courage to ask questions, if not, the passivity will grow. Therefore, communicative culture is also a practical manifestation of ethical culture [7][8].

The fourth layer is context. The same phrase can be perceived differently in different situations. The audience, purpose, timing, cultural background, and an organization’s internal rules all create context. Criticism delivered during a lesson differs from criticism expressed in public; in management, feedback given privately differs fundamentally from a harsh reprimand in a general meeting. Sensitivity to context is the ability to read the situation, feel the audience, and consciously answer the questions “when, where, to whom, and how.” Communication that ignores context often turns into conflict because it may intrude upon a person’s psychological boundaries [9][10].

Without seeing this system in its entirety, developing communicative culture is difficult. It is precisely here that the advantage of the competency-based approach becomes evident. The competency-based approach does not merely “explain” communicative culture; it constructs it as an outcome that can be tested, observed, and assessed in real situations. In other words, one can “know” by listening to a lecture, but communication can only be learned through practice. This resembles sports: reading theory does not guarantee victory in competition; continuous training, reflection, and analysis are required.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The communicative culture of management personnel, students in the formation of priority areas has been investigated by many scholars in the research and practices of pedagogy, linguistics, psychology. Within this research, scientific sources concerning communicative competence, competency-based education, and managerial communication have been analyzed. This works were the basis for identifying the theoretical basis and structural components of communicative culture, as well as mechanism for its development in the educational process.

First, the theoretical foundations of the concept of communicative competence were developed by the American scholar Dell Hymes. In his concept of “Communicative Competence,” he emphasized that language knowledge is not limited to grammatical competence; the ability to use language units appropriately in social contexts is also essential. According to Hymes, an individual should know when, with whom, in what form, and for what purpose to speak. This approach demonstrates that, in forming communicative culture, social and cultural competences are as important as linguistic knowledge [3][4].

Subsequently, M. Canale and M. Swain further developed the theory of communicative competence and clarified its structural components. Their studies indicate that communicative competence consists of four core components: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence. They argue that effective communication requires not only knowledge of language rules, but also the ability to organize discourse logically, overcome difficulties arising in interaction, and employ communicative strategies[11][12].

Another scholar who studied communicative competence in depth is L. Bachman. He views communicative competence as the unity of language competence and strategic competence. Bachman emphasizes that communicative competence is linked to an individual's ability to analyze communicative situations, plan speech activity, and manage the communication process. Such practice vividly emphasizes the positive importance of analytical vision and planning experience in communicative culture.

Origins of Competency-based Approach in Education By J. Raven Writing in "Competence in Modern Society" Raven defines competence in the following way: the ability of individuals to perform effectively in complex situations. He regards competency not simply as a body of knowledge and skills, but an integrative concept associated with motivation, values, and social experience. This theory indicates that the formation of communicative culture must take into account the individual's motivation, values, and social experience [13].

One of the scholars who researched competency-based education is A. Khutorskiy. He describes competency-based education as a pedagogical model that ensures learners' preparedness for practical activity. Khutorskiy stresses the importance of developing key competencies in education and presents communicative competence as a crucial factor enabling successful participation in social activity [14][15].

Peter Drucker writes extensively on communication in management. According to Drucker, communication is a key element in the overall success of an organization. He believes that establishing the best possible interaction with the team is one of the key responsibilities of a leader. He stresses that clarity, trust, and mutual respect here matter in managerial type communication.

We find a similar reflection of psychological dimensions of communicative culture in emotionally intelligence of Daniel Goleman. Goleman defines emotional intelligence as an individual's ability to manage one's own emotions, understand others' emotions, and build effective social relationships. He asserts that effective communication largely depends on the level of emotional intelligence, which is especially important in management.

Modern pedagogical research emphasizes the effectiveness of interactive methods in developing communicative culture. As an illustration R. Fisher and W. Ury base their negotiation culture studies on an approach to addressing conflict constructively through interest-based negotiation. They say that an effective way of communication is the analysis of interest not the position. This method is in good for managing appropriate communication in both managing and education.

Studies on communicative competence and the competency-based approach have also been extensively analyzed in Uzbek pedagogical literature. Research in the local area highlights how a mastery of communicative competence in education grows independent learners who think analytically and critically, and act socially. These studies are well-grounded to argue that the national education system should adopt implement the competency-based approach.

In general, the literature considered in the work shows that the communicative culture is a polyfunctional competence that is vital in professional activity. And this leads to the competency-based approach being one of the best pedagogical models to form this competence. These theoretical foundations served as the methodological basis for developing mechanisms to enhance the communicative culture of management personnel and students in subsequent stages of the study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The qualitative pedagogical research design of the study was aimed at researching the process of the communicative culture formation of the management personnel and students within the framework of a competency-based approach in higher education. The study was performed in the setting of a university atmosphere and is besides concerned with the methodical act of communicative competence via teaching and practice functions. Methodology — The data were collected from pedagogical observation and analysis of educational practices and a review of theoretical and methodological sources on communicative competence, management communication and competency-based education. The focus was mainly on how people communicate with each other (both during the same classes, discussions, trainings, and management-related communication situations). Observations of students and management personnel, while indulging in interactive learning activities it includes discussions, role-playing exercises, and communication trainings in studying empirically the fields, helped to identify key competencies affecting communicative culture. The

analysis thus included a modeling of pedagogic norms and a comparison of communicative situations in academic and managerial spheres to identify how principles of communicative competence tend to operate in theory as contrasted with practice. Elements of situational analysis were also drawn upon to explore typical communication problems and the communicative approaches used to solve them in a constructive manner. Objective: To analyze communicative behavior and competence, and the effectiveness of a competency-based learning technique, using data collected on second-year nursing students. Results Analysis was interpreted in the context of the theoretical background of communicative competence and competency-based education that allowed detection of effective pedagogical mechanisms for development of communicative culture of students and management personnel. This method allowed for the investigation of the coincidence of theory and practice in the formation of professional communication in higher education institutions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Forming communicative culture within a competency-based approach requires an integral connection between theoretical knowledge and practical activity. This study analyzed the structural model of communicative culture and the effective mechanisms for its development. The results indicate that communicative competence consists of several interrelated components.

1. A competency-based model of communicative culture. In order to develop communicative culture effectively within a competency-based approach, it is necessary to divide it into components that can be observed and assessed in practice. In this study, communicative culture was interpreted as a system of the following key competencies.

First is the competence of meaning and reasoning in logic. This skill demonstrates a person's ability to communicate his or her thoughts in a coherent, concise, and logical fashion. This competence plays a key role in management, and on students, it depends on the participation in academic discussions. Major markers of communicative culture, idea structuring, evidence, and the ability to adjust the speech to the audience's level of knowledge.

The second is communication ethics and values competence. And communicative culture is not just in the speech technique; it is also based on the ethical principle of respect, fairness and responsibility. By way of example, the communicative ethics of a debate may be identified by raising the issue, not the individual. To secure stability in management and education in particular such communication, bringing unsolicited views and positive attitude towards the opinions of others having to provide access to information in a nondiscriminatory manner and thereby strengthening the tolerance among the individuals concerns to opinions and views.

The third element is the competence of active listening and feedback. Modern communication studies suggest that it is not just having the speaking culture that is paramount to effective interaction, but the listening culture as well. Active listening involves asking relevant questions, paraphrasing, and responding considerately. For example, the "I-message" technique that allows one to talk about the problem without blaming the other person and thereby relieving psychological tension in communication.

The fourth is the ability to resolve and negotiate conflict. Differences are a natural part of management and education, not a bug, and the goal is to work through them productively. Highly communicative culture is manifested in avoiding personalization of conflict, addressing the essence of the problem, analysing interests and making decision on compromises.

Fifth is communication, both in a digital form, and in written form. In contemporary times, influenced by the information technologies, the electronic environments where a significant part of the communication is provided. As a result, the culture of written communication (by e-mail, official papers, social networks or chat rooms) is part of the communicative competence [1]. Its hallmarks include brevity, clarity, the use of evidence and ability to follow stylistic rules.

The key feature of this model is that it is equally applicable to management personnel and students; the context may be more complex. Seminar discussions or scientific presentations are key domains for communicative competence for students; team meetings and internal negotiations are the equivalent for managers.

2. Practical situation analysis: points of intersection between managers and students. During the study, practical manifestations of communicative culture were analyzed through different scenarios. These scenarios reveal communicative problems common to both management systems and educational processes.

In the first scenario, when criticism is delivered in an inappropriate manner, a decline in motivation is observed. For example, a leader or teacher may tell an employee or student: "You are always late; you are irresponsible." Although this statement points to a problem, it contains two major communicative errors: overgeneralization and personal attack. As a result, the interlocutor assumes a defensive stance and communication does not continue constructively.

A competency-based approach recommends the “fact – impact – expectation” model in such cases. For example: “Over the past two weeks, you were late to three meetings. As a result, the discussion process was interrupted. In the future, please arrive five minutes early.” This is a situation-based and not a person-based and has a solution-oriented approach.

The second situation arises when reports are being discussed. Argumentation among students and business managers over debates then shifts focus from pragmatic analytical reasoning to an ego competition. As a result, there is an escalation in tension or sarcasm and emotional responses. Having a discussion regulation framework is crucial to manage these conditions. Dividing roles between panelists—for a debate within a class, for example, one could be a moderator, an evidence checker, a summarizer, a timekeeper, etc.—can keep things orderly and efficient. Thus, it prioritizes evidence over personal confrontation.

The third scenario has to do with digital. Often, short words are taken out of context in contemporary management and education. Like for example a brief message like “Get her here. Now.” can be seen as an order — and even as offensive. So good digital communication etiquette can help to prevent such cases, i.e. addressing more appropriately, providing context or positioning more effectively and negotiating the timing increases productivity. For instance: “Ms. Khonzoda, I have a small issue to discuss with you. May I come by at 15:00?” maintains a respectful tone.

3. Competency-based formation technology: practice and reflection. Developing communicative culture is not limited to mastering theoretical knowledge. The findings show that practical exercises and reflection play a decisive role in shaping competence.

At the first stage, a brief theoretical explanation is provided. For example, active listening consists of clarifying questions, paraphrasing, and understanding emotional states.

At the second stage, situational exercises are organized. For example, a student expresses dissatisfaction about a scholarship issue, or an employee approaches a manager regarding workload. Participants perform roles and apply communicative strategies in practice.

At the third stage, assessment criteria are applied. Asking questions, listening, giving constructive feedback, and problem-solving are evaluated through special rubrics.

Stage four is reflective analysis. Participants interpret the tone, expressions, and tactics used in an interaction. This process aids in pinpointing errors in the communication and developing means to mitigate them in the future.

By institutionalising this cycle, communicative culture moves from a stage of knowing to one of doing. This is one of the key output of the competency-based approach.

4. Outcomes you can expect in education and management settings. The findings show that pursuit of communicative competence in a planned and systematic manner has been associated with benefits.

At the personal developmental level, whether that be a student or employee, you are developing the ability to clearly explain your ideas, listen to other people, and think when your emotions are high. This helps interaction in the field of work.

Second, at the team level, the quality of internal communication in an organization increases. Meetings become more productive, conflicts are resolved constructively, and a psychologically safe environment develops.

Third, at the institutional level, the efficiency of education and management systems improves. Written and oral communication becomes more standardized, internal conflicts decrease, and overall productivity increases.

Thus, forming communicative culture on the basis of a competency-based approach emerges as an important pedagogical and social factor that enhances the effectiveness of both management systems and higher education institutions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The competency-based approach is one of the most appropriate ways to form the communicative culture of management personnel and students because it treats communication not as a theoretical concept, but as professional activity manifested in real situations. To develop communicative culture effectively, it is necessary to ensure: (a) a clear competence model, (b) regular use of situational exercises, (c) assessment through rubrics, and (d) an established reflection mechanism.

Practical analyses demonstrate that conflicts often escalate not due to the “issue” itself but due to communication style; motivation often begins not with “rewards” but with respect and fair feedback; team effectiveness often grows not from “resources” but from clear agreements and communicative order. Therefore, in higher education institutions and organizations, forming communicative culture should not be viewed as a separate course or a one-time training event, but as a continuous competence integrated into the education–management process.

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